

heterosis was also high in V20 A/IR36, especially for MR at flowering.

Pn/MR in IR54752 A/IR54 showed marginal positive heterosis at the vegetative stage and was negative at flowering. Both hybrids showed negative

standard heterosis over Swarnaprabha in Pn/MR, especially at flowering.

These results suggest that selecting restorers to reduce MR and improve Pn and Pn/MR would increase photosynthetic productivity. □

Photosynthetic rate (Pn) and maintenance respiration (MR)^a of F₁ rice hybrids in Cuttack, India, 1990 dry season.^b

Hybrid	Vegetative			Flowering		
	Pn	MR	Pn/MR	Pn	MR	Pn/MR
IR54752 A/IR54	45.3 (24)	1.66 (17)	27.2 (6)	33.4 (6)	1.23 (19)	27.1 (-11)
V20 A/IR36	46.1 (36)	1.80 (25)	25.6 (9)	34.7 (26)	1.46 (23)	23.7 (2)
Swarnaprabha	36.2	1.28	28.3	29.6	0.90	32.8
LSD(0.05)	3.4	0.11		1.9	0.12	
Standard heterosis						
IR54752 A/IR54	25	29	4	13	36	-17
V20 A/IR36	27	40	-10	17	62	-28

^aPn and MR in mg CO₂/dm² per h. ^bFigures in parentheses = heterosis over restorer.

Effect of low light on F₁ rice hybrids

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F₁ rice hybrids are reported to be more productive than elite conventional varieties even under such stresses as drought and salinity. Low light is another major constraint to rice production during the rainy season.

We studied tolerance for low light in hybrids IR54752 A/IR54 and V20 A/IR36 and their restorers, with standard checks Ratna and Swarnaprabha during 1990 dry season. The crop was grown in 1.2-m² field plots at 15- × 10-cm plant spacing and fertilized with 80 kg N/ha.

Low light (50% sunlight) condition was imposed from 40 d after planting to harvest by shading with wood screens. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 420 cal/cm² per d). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Growth durations were 128 d in all treatments.

The hybrids showed positive heterosis in total dry matter and yield over the restorer parent under low light only (see table).

Yield and heterosis in yield were higher for IR54752 A/IR54 than for V20 A/IR36.

Effect of low light (50% of normal) from 40 d after planting to harvest on dry matter and yield of F₁ rice hybrid restorers and check varieties. Cuttack, India.

Cultivar	Total dry matter (g/m ²)		Yield (g/m ²)	
	Full light	Low light	Full light	Low light
Hybrid				
IR54752 A/IR54	985	643	418	206
V20 A/IR36	853	471	345	167
Restorers				
IR54	993	537	426	179
IR36	853	427	400	164
Checks				
Ratna	803	358	354	144
Swarnaprabha	928	597	480	243
Mean	902	506	403	183
LSD(0.05)				
Variety	99		17	
Treatment	57		44	
Variety × treatment	ns		ns	
Heterosis over restorer				
IR54752 A/IR54	-1	19	-2	15
V20 A/IR36	0	11	-13	2
Standard heterosis				
IR54152 A/IR54 vs				
Ratna	22	79	18	43
Swarnaprabha	6	8	-13	-15
V20 A/IR36 vs				
Ratna	6	33	-3	16
Swarnaprabha	8	-20	-28	-31

This could be associated with the higher yield potential of restorer IR54. The hybrids also showed strong standard heterosis over Ratna under low light, but negative heterosis in yield over Swarnaprabha, a low light-tolerant variety. □

Analysis of heterotic relationships among quantitative characters of hybrid rice

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In 1987, we used 6 male sterile lines and 12 fertility restorer lines to make 72 F₁ hybrid combinations. A field experiment Apr-Oct 1988 was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications, with 30 plants per plot. Row and hill spacing was 17 × 23 cm. The center five plants in each plot were sampled.

Eleven characters were analyzed (Table 1): days to heading (DH), culm number/plant (CN), panicle length (PL, cm), plant height (PH, cm), total spikelet number/panicle (TSN), filled spikelet number/panicle (FSN), filled spikelet percentage (FSP), 1,000-grain weight (GW, g), biological yield/plant (BY, g), grain-straw ratio (GSR), and grain yield/plant (GY, g). Heterosis was estimated for each character as

$$H = F_1 - (P_1 + P_2)/2$$

Correlation coefficient and stepwise regression analysis were used to estimate relationships among characters.

Correlations varied with character combinations; 31 were significant (Table 1). In the F₁ hybrids, correlations of DH to TSN and FSN; CN to BY; PL to PH, FSN, GW, and BY; PH to TSN, FSN, and BY; TSN to FSN and BY, FSN to FSP, BY, and GSR; FSP to GSR; GW to GSR; and CY to CN, PL, PH, FSN, FSP, GW, BY, and GSR were positive and significant; those of DH to GW, CN to TSN and FSN, and TSN to FSP, GW, and GSR were negative and significant.

Some of the character combinations had more or less the same correlation trends, except that more character combinations showed significant correlations in the F₁ hybrids than in the parents, particularly GSR, which had negative correlation (although nonsignificant) in the parents with PL, FSN, FSP, GW, and BY but showed positive correlation